

Performance, Learning, and Social Justice: Theorizing HRD Practices in the International Training Office Yesterday, Today, and Tomorrow

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Using the critical perspective, this research studies the International Training Office's (ITO) changing HRD practices. It presents the organizational characteristics, context, and practices of ITO across three timeframes and analyzes the appropriateness of these practices for its context and makes recommendations for enhancing its effectiveness. This longitudinal study uses participant observation, archival research and interview. Management and staff engage in dialectical critical dialogue advancing HRD practices that promotes performance, learning, and social justice cultivating empowerment.

Keywords: Change, Organizational Culture, Collaboration/Teaming and Leadership

Introduction

Research Problems

At best, HRD is practiced as a deliberate institutional effort in big for-profit and not-for-profit institutions. At worst, HRD in small organizations is not practiced at all. But for many organizations, HRD is unplanned or practiced indirectly, unintentionally, or intuitively. The top brass of organizations engages in annual strategic planning but its content and process are not systematically relayed to all members of the organization so that everyone could be "on the same page" in terms of the current and long-term directions of the organization. Organizational learning for lower-echelon employees becomes incidental and anecdotal.

General Purpose

This is a research on organizational culture (Martin & Meyerson, 1988) and organizational meaning making (Donnellon, Gray, & Bougon, 1986). An award-winning prior scholarly work (Dutton & Dukerich, 1991) built the foundation upon which I was motivated to conduct a similar qualitative research that examines the way by which social actors perceive and affect organizational changes. The general purpose of this study is to investigate how social actors make sense of significant matters affecting strategic change in organizational HRD practices. It analytically traces the circuitous development of organizational identity that the organizational actors formulate, appreciating the HRD practices of ITO in order to help intentionally facilitate the placement and implementation of systematic critical HRD practices that make ITO a learning organization practicing social justice that promotes organizational development, systematizes knowledge management, and encourages organizational learning. I argue that organizational identity affects actors' interpretation for action but also these interpretations likewise affect organizational action over time.

Research Questions

This paper raises the following questions:

1. What are the organizational and contextual features of ITO?
2. What are the changing HRD practices of ITO?
3. How appropriate are the HRD practices of ITO?
4. How can ITO improve its HRD practices?

Theoretical Framework

I use critical theory as a tool to view HRD. Critical theory is a framework that examines power relations and takes into consideration class, ethnicity, and gender in social analysis (Cunningham, 1992, 2000). I consider the definition of HRD by Swanson & Holton (2001) as important but incomplete, as it does not consider many factors important to my analysis. Therefore, I propose to redefine HRD to mean the following. As a product of clashing social forces and ideologies, human resource development (HRD) is a pro-active, forward-looking process that responds to social forces as well as overhauls organizational and social structures. It taps inter-individual human potentials and talents as well as takes into consideration gender, ethnicity, class, environment and other critical issues, thereby paving the way for a new transformed organizational and social order that promotes social justice

and lasting peace. Critical HRD takes into account social justice, where all persons in an organization are engaged in participatory collaboration, are treated fairly, receive just share in the benefits of the organization, and are equally recognized for all their contributions to the development of the organization.

Definition of HRD

Swanson & Holton (2001, p. 4) defined human resource development as “a process for developing and unleashing human expertise through organization development and personnel training and development for the purpose of improving performance.” The above definition is useful and performance is indeed an essential but not sufficient purpose of HRD. However, other authors disagree with Swanson & Holton (2001) and argue that the purpose of HRD is not performance but learning (Watkins & Marsick, 1997). There are also eclectics who contend that the purpose of HRD is both performance and learning (Chalofsky, 1990; Gilley & Maycunich, 2000; Nadler & Nadler, 1989). I agree that performance and learning are important purposes of HRD. But something is missing: where is the social justice (Cunningham, 1998)?

Objectives of HRD

There are two contending schools of thought regarding the objectives of HRD. On the one hand, the first school of thought stresses performance as the purpose of HRD. On the other hand, the second school of thought emphasizes learning as the purpose of HRD. But, in the debate, where is the social justice? On the surface, the debate is between one purpose and another purpose. However, upon deeper reflection, I realized that the debate is not only theoretical but ideological, as critical theorists see it. Missing in the debate is the element of ideology. I add the meta-theory of ideology to explain the debates among practitioners regarding the objectives of HRD. Using ideology as my meta-theory and influenced by critical theory, I consider social justice as the objective of HRD, not just performance or learning.

Meta-Theory and the Ensuing Ideological Debates

Although I use critical theory to view HRD, I differ with the ways by which other critical theorists view HRD. Critical theorists in general simply lump together and dismiss both performance and learning as objectives that serve the interest of the capitalists in particular and of the powerful in general. However, I make a distinction between conservative and libertarian HRD. I classify the first school of thought as conservative and the second school of thought as libertarian.

The first school of thought in HRD is conservative because by stressing performance, the underlying importance is placed on the need for all employees to improve their productivity and therefore increase the bottom line for the benefit of the corporate or institutional interest. Thus, the concern is for the workers to serve the interest of capital or the higher authorities. In addition, there is no change in the relative position between the top institutional or corporate echelon and the employees. For all these reasons, HRD that stresses performance is conservative. Libertarian HRD, however, stresses the importance of learning, both institutional and individual. As opposed to conservative HRD, libertarian HRD sees the importance of employees and their contributions to the well-being of the institution or corporation. The focus is not just the top echelon or the institution as such, but also the employees. Critics of libertarian HRD sarcastically label this approach as touchy-feely, making the employees feel good but without any real impact either on the productivity of the employees or on the increase in the profits of corporate or institutional interests. Critical HRD, however, digs deeper into the foundation or structure of power relations within an institution and raises the question of social justice and equality. Instead of maintaining power relations the way conservative HRD does, critical HRD builds power from the bottom and empowers the workers. Furthermore, critical HRD is concerned not with the touchy-feely aspects of pacifying workers to make them feel they are listened to, but actually takes into account the contributions of the workers to the overall development of the institution. Third, critical HRD is concerned not with profit but with social justice, equality, and the common good in the bigger society at large. The concern, therefore, is social change that transforms individuals, groups, and communities for the advancement of social interests. I study ITO from the perspective of critical HRD.

HRD Functions

In this paper, I investigate the HRD functions of ITO diachronically. Basically, I scrutinize the HRD practices of ITO over time, instead of just treating the HRD practices of ITO as static and unchangeable. I divide the HRD practices of ITO into three periods: period one starts from August 16, 2004 and ends in August 15, 2005, while period two starts from August 16, 2005 and ends in August 15, 2006, and period three starts from August 16, 2006 and ends in August 15, 2007. I describe, analyze and synthesize the merits and demerits of the HRD practices of ITO in these three time frames. Using critical theory, I study the following HRD functions in these three periods. These functions include training and development; learning organization, organizational learning, and knowledge management; performance improvement; organizational development; and, strategic HRD.

Methodology

Revisiting Dutton & Dukerich's award-winning article (1991), this paper used a situated and relational methodology that empirically delves into the impact of organizational actors on organizational development. This work described and explained how actors make sense of the organizational strategies, after which a new perspective of organizational adaptation is constructed. In this paper, I generated a typology of organizational knowledge, which portrayed the distinction between prior knowledge, current knowledge, and developing knowledge. This situated and relational investigation provided a nuanced discernment of how prior work contoured continuing knowledge creation and development. This work employed a grounded approach to theory building, which entered into a dialogue with the pertinent literature to answer the research questions, regarding shifting organizational roles. It used the qualitative case study method and ethnography in order to obtain information regarding multiple views and organizational culture, respectively, upon which to build theory where little data existed. For data analysis, following Dutton & Dukerich (1991), I (1) used a summary form to record my findings, (2) developed a complete thematic list, (3) coded the data onto the themes, and (4) constructed my taxonomy. As a diachronic or longitudinal study, the changing practices of ITO are studied from my point of view as an employee based on the different time frames during which I am employed. To accomplish this research, I used a combination of data sources. First, I did an analysis and synthesis of archival documents. To fill in the gaps, I conducted interviews with key personnel with HRD functions, namely Dr. L. Ong and Dr. J. Gajanayake. In addition, I engaged in participant observation as I am employed in ITO since 2004. This paper is divided into four sections: (1) organizational characteristics and context of the organization, (2) description of the HRD practices in the organization, (3) analysis of the appropriateness of the practices, and (4) recommendations for improving HRD practices.

Results and Findings

Organizational Characteristics and Context of International Training Office

The Division of International Programs (IP, 2006) of Northern Illinois University enters into international agreements with foreign governmental and non-governmental institutions as well as universities. The International Training Office (ITO) in particular, which is a part of IP, engages in international education and training that makes its participants become catalysts of change. In its mission statement, ITO (2006) declares that it is committed to strengthening the capacities of international professionals and leaders from public, non-profit, or private sector organizations to become catalysts for change in their home countries. ITO accomplishes this mission through innovative training programs and outreach activities that address institutional, professional, and societal needs.

ITO has a global reach, as its beneficiaries come from every part of the world. It also has a grassroots reach, as its beneficiaries come from not only national capital cities but also from the remotest villages and islands in the different continents of the world. Its programs deal with both (1) social structures such as classes, gender, and ethnicity as well as (2) culture such as religious values. These programs do not only seek to lead to individual changes but more importantly to organizational and social transformation that reduce conflict and promote harmony. They deal with micro-level (such as interpersonal interaction), middle-level (organizations), and macro-level (class structure and shared meanings) analysis. Not only highly educated, well experienced, and very qualified but more importantly very humble and open-minded persons who have primary HRD roles in ITO run the organization, without whom critical HRD changes cannot take place.

HRD Practices of International Training Office Then

Using critical theory, I scrutinize the HRD practices of ITO in the following areas in this section: (1) training and development, (2) learning organization, organizational learning, and knowledge management, (3) performance improvement, (4) organization development, and (5) strategic HRD. The academic year 2004-2005 was a time during which I had to learn the ropes about ITO from scratch on my own. The work is participatory and dialogic: while management issued a list of tasks to be performed, staff members gave their feedback and made suggestions. Management publicly recognized the contributions staff members made and implemented them; thus, social justice was practiced.

Training and Development. When I started working at ITO in 2004, there was no internal staff training and development. The only time there was a formal meeting was when I was short-listed and interviewed for the job. I did not have a strategic view of the whole organization. I did jobs as they came along. The director is extremely organized and distributed a task map for things all the employees had to perform for a specific program. For instance, when the Philippine program was to be implemented in early April, the employees received the task map as early as during the first week of January. The tasks were organized chronologically so that the employees all knew the things that have to be accomplished in succession. Sometimes, I would spend a lot of time performing a task just to be told later that there is a better way of doing it. Such was the case with preparing the transportation

schedule and reservations. However, had I known earlier that there is a good standard template that I can use, I would have used my working hours more efficiently and done other things as well.

ITO as a Learning Organization. When I came to ITO in 2004, I had to reinvent the wheel in everything I did. I repeatedly requested a former employee who graduated and left NIU to let me know what the standard practices were. He only always said: "It's easy. You can do it on your own." All my efforts to learn the ropes from the former employee were in vain. In fact, he did not want to give me the room key and I had to constantly ask for the office key. He told me I did not need the key as he will come to the office, even after his contract has expired and so I got so confused but could not verbalize my frustrations. Finally I got the key after about a month's time, reminding him and my supervisor that he was no longer employed with our office. He also did not want to give up the voice mail in the office telephone and I had to struggle to find out how to change the voice mail and the name registered on the office phone line. Based on the above, there was no transfer of skills from the former employee to the new employee as such. There was no institutional memory that could be passed on to the next employees, as the memory belonged to the individual who left the office. Thus, employees were engaged in knee-jerk response and produced reactive solutions at best. Employees had to engage in "learning by doing" about ITO and its standard operations from scratch. During the implementation of training programs, staff members had to do everything, such as moving equipment and supplies to the session hall before the session begins and pack up as well as move the equipment and supplies back to the office after office hours. Other pieces of equipment that the office does not possess have to be rented on a daily basis. Many resource persons submit their handouts on the eve of their presentations. Employees had to make photocopies oftentimes after midnight so that the documents will be ready the next morning. Moreover, employees had to attend the sessions so that they can prepare a write-up not only about the content but also the flow of each session. Scheduling was erratic: for instance, there was no clear pattern as to when one works. Staff members had to "run after" participants to collect their daily journals, for instance, which are often written on the very last minute. In addition, when training programs are in session, employees willingly worked day and night as well as weekdays and weekends, when their academic schedules permitted them. Furthermore, before I came to work at ITO, other employees informed me that staff members do substantive presentations or give the same lectures that NIU faculty or staff present but were not given any honorarium. In summary, I did incidental on-the-job learning about what things are and how things are done.

Performance Management. In terms of performance, there was no way we failed in performing our tasks. Early on, each employee was given a task map to be executed in connection with the conduct of a training program. By hook or by crook, we had to learn how to do things on our own. There was no manual to read or to follow. There were no written precedents to follow. Each employee's internal incentive was to make sure that no aspect of the preparation must fail so that the program implementation will be successful. As a consequence, employees voluntarily and eagerly worked overtime and weekends without pay in order to catch up with the work load.

Organization Development. Despite the difficulties new employees encountered, the lines of communication between the top-level management and the lowest-level staff members were always open. Employees approached management often to solve problems, seek solutions or get answers to questions about matters to which they must attend. Employees got a sense of organizational culture by gut feel. Employees offer suggestions on both the content and methods of operations to which management listens. Thus, there was a healthy feedback loop. Not only did management listen to employees but top management also implemented changes based on some of the suggestions of employees, which empowered the latter. This was an important sign that management and employees were engaged in critical dialogue which empowered both the top-level management and bottom-level employees. Thus, critical HRD, which recognizes social justice, was in operation.

Strategic HRD. The directors of these three offices and the executive director meet annually for their annual evaluation of the work of the individual offices under IP and the work of IP in general as well as engage in strategic planning. As far as ITO is concerned, employees are asked to give their inputs and feedback to the agenda items that are discussed during the annual executive evaluation and planning meeting. Employees hear of bits and pieces of the directions for the coming year, as discussed by members of the executive meeting. Each office under IP, including ITO, links HRD with strategic goals in order to improve performance as well as promote change.

In summary, the dominant structure that management imposed was the system under which employees operated. There was a static equilibrium in which the organization functioned according to the laid down directives and tasks to be performed. Nevertheless, grassroots workers suggested some changes that management accepted and put in place. However, employees see the need for improvement in some areas that need intervention which were later recommended to management. Thus, participatory efforts for change were at its embryonic stage.

Analysis of the Appropriateness of the Practice: HRD Practices of ITO Now

The top-level management of IP, which includes the executive director and the directors of the three offices within its umbrella, has a strategic view of the whole organization. They meet regularly as well as annually in order

to evaluate and plan the direction for the coming year. Employees focus working on their individual tasks, although occasionally members of each office work in tandem with members of the other offices in specific annual projects, such as during (1) the Study Abroad Fair, (2) International Week, (3) the Flag Parade, and (4) ISFO international student orientation. Other than that, employees, however, do not have a strategic view of the organization's vision, direction, or priorities in terms of substance or working operations: both IP as the larger organization or ITO as the specific organization. Thus, there is room for change.

From the academic year 2005 to 2006, grassroots employees have proposed some concrete changes to management for the benefit of the organization. For various reasons, management accepted some suggestions and rejected others. Below are some changes that were implemented, after they were proposed to the management, which were the result of an informal action research. Management and staff are constantly engaged in critical and participatory dialogue about the operations of the office. Social justice is in place, as grassroots employees' recommendations and contributions are not only recognized but also put into action.

Training and Development. In the past, there was no training. Employees jump in to the job and perform tasks. If they are not sure about what to do, they ask management for trouble-shooting and problem-solving. However, there is now a system of coaching, mentoring and apprenticeship. New employees, extra help, interns and volunteers have some pieces of documents to refer to, such as an Office Manual and cheat sheets, which guide them to understand the mission of ITO, the objectives of the program, and the specific tasks to be performed (Ty, 2006b).

ITO as a Learning Organization. In the immediate past year, employees had to learn how to do things on their own. However, some changes were instituted at this stage. Aside from coaching and mentoring new recruits, ITO has a whole set of encoded standard operating procedures (SOPs) in an office manual called *International Training Office as a Learning Organization: Knowledge Management and Organizational Learning* (Ty, 2006b). The manual lists down the rights and duties of workers, what are the things employees are expected to do in general as well as things employees need to do during the pre-conduct, conduct, and post-conduct stages of a program. Thus, the manual provides the training SOPs which makes the life of new hires, interns and volunteers easy. It also provides step-by-step cheat sheets on how things are done. The manual can be used in different ways: as a self-learning document, as a document that is used for training new workers, as well as a document to which employees can refer to guide them in their work. The manual is an effort at knowledge management so that information is not personal but institutional. By so doing, all employees can be engaged in organizational learning.

In the past, employees had to photocopy all documents which were often given on the eve of the resource person's lecture. As a consequence, workers at times had to make photocopies in the wee hours of the night and give these copies to the participants early in the morning—prior to the start of the morning's session. These documents are distributed as stand-alone documents which will not leave any institutional memory, as they tend to be filed away amidst a pile of documents. No books were produced. Now, however, employees ask resource persons to submit their handouts and PowerPoint files by electronic mail at least two weeks prior to the conduct of a training program. These documents are then compiled in a compendium with a proper cover page, title page, table of contents, continuous pagination and are bound in book form. What are the advantages that are produced as a result of this intentional change? One, no precious time is wasted on just making photocopies constantly of separate documents which are submitted at different points in time. This in turn frees workers to use their time more efficiently to work on other matters. Two, participants can take back to their home countries a tangible material that can be used as a sourcebook for their transfer of learning. At the end of programs, employees collectively write a book, copies of which are sent to participants in their home countries. Three, by preparing training manuals and books, ITO is engaged in knowledge management. Bound copies of training materials are by nature organized sets of documents. Copies are sent to the Library of Congress and select libraries which will benefit more readers and practitioners alike. Intentional changes as discussed above have been put in place.

Performance Management. In the past, performance was guaranteed by the issuance of a task map. Based on the tasks assigned to them, all employees knew what they were doing since the start of each semester. Each employee has the incentive not to fail in performing their tasks in order to ensure that programs run smoothly. Now, employees recommended that "tasks" be reworded as "delegation of powers and responsibilities," to which management consented. Workers did exactly the same work, whether it is called a "task" or a "power." What are the advantages that are generated as a consequence of this intentional change? Two important things happened here. One, management listened to the feedback of the workers and acted on it. Two, the change in terminology is not merely descriptive but substantive. The words "power" and "responsibilities" are more empowering to the workers than the word "task." For these two reasons, social justice is practiced in the office as lower-level employees can initiate change that management listens to and accepts. Management and staff are engaged in participatory organizational and human resource development. On another issue, workers in the past had erratic work schedules during program implementation. Upon the recommendation of employees, each person now is assigned either

morning shift or afternoon shift, based on their other study, work, or family obligations. What is the benefit of this intentional change in scheduling? Now, there is order in the way by which individuals schedule their life activities. In what ways has performance improved as a result of this intentional change? Aside from making these and many other recommendations, grassroots employees write project proposals which successfully obtain funding (Ty, 2006a). They also co-author books and are formally recognized in the publications for their efforts. Low-level employees get formal and public recognition for their accomplishments and achievements which is another proof that social justice is practiced in the office. Based on the foregoing statements, employees and management are truly engaged in participatory human resource and organizational development that improves performance.

Organization Development. Management listens to and applies the recommendations from the bottom up, which empowers the workers. What are some of the intentional changes that took place in the past and continually occur today in the organization? Today, employees are engaged in proposal writing, program management, developing programs, selecting resource persons, scheduling, monitoring program implementation, supervising interns and volunteers, and coaching contractual extra help. Changes come from top down, bottom up, as well as horizontally. All these changes advance organizational development. Many of these recommendations solve problems, support organizational culture, encourage learning and ameliorate performance and at the same time promote social justice.

Strategic HRD. With all of these changes in place, there appears to be the seeds of active, intentional, and participatory efforts at strategic HRD. In the past, employees were always catching up, learning as they worked along, and responding only to the specific needs of the moment. Today, employees participate and are involved in thinking pro-actively and therefore have a longer view of the contents and methods of the ITO work over the long haul.

Table 1. *Performance, Learning, and Social Justice: Theorizing HRD Practices Then, Now, and in the Immediate Future*

HRD Practices	Changing Human Resource Development Practices Over Time Seen and Practiced from the Organizational Actor's Perspective		
Factors			
Main Purpose	Performance	Learning	Social Justice
Phases	One	Two	Three
Years	HRD Practices Then, 2004-2005	Intentional Changes in HRD Practices, 2005-2006	Recommended Further Intentional Changes in HR Practice, 2006-2007
Membership Stages	Neophyte Member	Integrated Member	Deepening Member
System Theories	Static Equilibrium	Dynamic Equilibrium	Disequilibrium
Training and Development	Self-Learning	Start Coaching and Mentoring	Improve Coaching and Mentoring
Learning Organization	Individual Reinvention of the Wheel, Learning by Doing	Knowledge Management, Standardized Office Manual	Continue Knowledge Management, Revise Standardized Office Manual
Performance Management	Fulfillment of the "Project Task Map," Multitasking	Fulfillment of the "Delegation of Powers and Responsibilities," Empowering Participants, Recruiting Volunteers and Interns	Participation in the "Delegation of Powers and Responsibilities," Empowering Participants, Continue Recruiting Volunteers and Interns
Organizational Development	Bottom-Up Feedback as a Source of Organizational Tweaking	Multidirectional Sources of Organizational Transformation	Institutionalize Multidirectional Sources of Organizational Transformation
Collaboration, Participation, and Agents of Change	Principally Top Down, Some Horizontal, Empowered Managers	Top Down and Horizontal, Participatory	Top Down, Horizontal, and Bottom Up, Participatory, and Mutually Empowering
Strategic HRD	Top-Level Strategic Planning & Lower-Level Reactive Change	Pro-Active Multi-Level Human Resource Development	Include More Long-Term Agenda in the Office Manual; Institutionalize Pro-Active Multi-Level HR Development
Where's the Social Justice?	In Existence	Strengthened	Further Strengthened

Summary of the Comparative Analysis of Appropriateness. HRD practices of ITO both in the past and now had an effective performance management system, as line management had ownership of the system while at the same time line management provided a fair process since management listened to the workers' suggestions and workers' feedback were welcome. The past practices were reactive and had a short-term view, as employees always strove to catch up with their work. All these have changed. The current practices, however, are pro-active and have a long-term view, as employees participate in developing materials that will have long-term impact, such as the training manual for new hires, the training manual, and the post-program book. A knowledge management system has been

intentionally been put in place which fosters greater organizational learning among all employees, especially new hires and contractual workers who need to understand in a short span of time the context and content of the organizational work. Furthermore, HRD practices in the past were mostly top down. Today, HRD practices are a combination of top down as well as bottom up and horizontal approaches, as peers make recommendations to one another as well.

Conclusion and Recommendations for Improving HRD Practices in the Immediate Future

Summary

This paper developed the constructs of organizational identity and organizational adaptation. Managing strategic organizational change demands a reflection of the impact of change on the organizational actors through which actual identities become destabilized and morph into envisioned images. This paper studied three time frames in the ever-changing HRD practices of ITO. Through the years, three themes emerged in the dialectical, not linear, development of ITO's HRD practices: performance, learning, and social justice. From 2004 to 2005, during which I started my first year of work with ITO, I was an outsider coming in, learning the ropes on how the office functioned. This paper shows that with the encouraging and constructive role of open-minded management, people-centered innovations were intentionally put to place that led to positive changes, such as total quality enhancement, in a dynamic organizational context. From 2005 to 2006, I became an insider and acquired a general sense of the contents and methods of the operations of ITO. Lowest-level employees have presented several ideas as well as made several concrete proposals to improve several HRD functions in HRD. From the bottom up, grassroots-level employees have specifically suggested changes to improve the performance and learning of employees and volunteers, which have been met with approval, recognition and praise by the highest-level management, thereby proving that social justice is practiced in ITO. As a result, critical HRD is practiced more and more.

From the academic year 2004-2005 to the academic year 2005-2006, there were notable changes in the HRD practices of ITO. I argue that the purposes of HRD are three-fold: not only performance and learning but also social justice. In terms of performance, employees are more satisfied with their work as they now have "powers and responsibilities," not just "tasks." They are now engaged in writing proposals, obtaining grants, preparing programs, as well as publishing books and training manuals, not just performing tasks as they had been doing in the past. In terms of learning, ITO is now a learning organization, as employees are engaged in organizational learning through the development and use of the office manual, which is an effort at knowledge management. In terms of social justice, management listens to and applies grassroots workers' initiatives. Management also gives public and formal recognition for the achievements of employees, such as writing proposals and obtaining grants for the effort. Effective intra-office communications, in the form of the above-mentioned creative problem solving and participatory decision making, made possible effective management, increased performance, improved learning, and greater respect for social justice.

Recommendations

The only thing that is permanent is change. Changes that will continue to be put in effect will surely lead to organizational revitalization. Many of the challenges of the past HRD practices were revised with the implementation of recommendations which employees proposed that the open-minded managers accepted. Workers uttered concerns to managers who gave a forum for their voice. In addition to the already implemented changes, I believe that ITO must continue to develop its long-term strategic view and work. While top management is engaged in strategic HRD work, employees at all levels must be informed of the decisions they make as well as take part in the decision-making process so that everyone in the organization will be "on the same page." Strategic HRD can only be successful if everyone knows, understands, accepts, and works on the same vision, mission and goals.

Contribution to New Knowledge in HRD

Using the equilibrium theory, most HRD texts discuss performance and learning as the purpose of HRD. Using the disequilibrium perspective, this research demonstrates that, aside from productivity and personal growth, another important purpose of HRD is missing in the literature of HRD, namely social justice. This longitudinal case study shows that continuing dialectical dialogue between managers and staff is important, that participatory practices is healthy and promotes positive transformation in HRD practices, that empowerment is continually negotiated, and that critical HRD promotes social justice that empowers managers, staff, and beneficiaries. Most importantly, this research contributes to new knowledge by using the disequilibrium model that focuses on social justice that hitherto was an untouchable and unspeakable terrain in HRD. Testing of the least explored theories of disequilibrium theory and critical HRD led to the results of this research.

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